

D8.7 - Dissemination and exploitation plan update

WP8 - Communication and dissemination

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MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Disclaimer: The views and opinions expressed in this report are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Abstract

This report presents the third iteration of the strategy and plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, adding a strategy and plan for scientific result dissemination. The report also includes an evaluation of the tools and tactics from D8.6, and adds a third iteration in the stepwise approach to the MINDtheGEPs communications strategy and plan: focusing on sharing results to mobilise and continue building our audiences.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	2023-07-13	Draft report		Review
V1.0	2023-07-31	Final report	Addressing review	Submission
V1.1	2023-11-27	Updated report	Adding publications agreement in Annex	Resubmission

Information in this report that may influence other MINDtheGEPs tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
T8.1 Communication and dissemination strategy and planning	This report is a first iteration of the communications strategy and plan
T8.2 Scientific dissemination	This report outlines scientific dissemination strategy and an initial dissemination plan.
T8.3 Exploitation and sustainability planning	This report includes an initial list of exploitable results.
T8.4 Communication tools and activities	This report lists a set of tools, tactics and activities
T8.5 Measuring outreach	This report includes an evaluation of metrics that have been fed back to T8.1

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1. Introduction

MINDtheGEPs takes a multidisciplinary multidimensional approach to challenging gender imbalances across five different countries: Italy, Spain, Serbia, Ireland, Poland. The project is implementing Gender Equality Plans (in this document also referred to as GEPs) across various types of research performing organisations, four of them public universities, one public non-academic research institute, one academic, and one private technological institute. The work to communicate and disseminate results from the project is led by Uppsala University (UPP) and Elsevier together. This report builds on strategy outlined in D8.1 – Visual identity and guidelines for use, D8.2 – Dissemination and communication plan, D8.6 – Dissemination and exploitation plan update, and D8.3 – Exploitation plan.

To ensure the strategy and plan are flexible and suit the needs of the project and its partners, MINDtheGEPs is using a three-step approach to Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation (DCE) strategy and plan. Due to the extension of the project by six months, the timelines described in the initial strategy and plan (D8.2) have been adjusted to accommodate the delivery of reports.

In the **initial phase** (M1-18), efforts were focused on identifying and connecting with stakeholders and gatekeepers to create awareness of the project and what it can be expected to produce. This work is described in D8.1 & D8.2.

In the **second phase** (M19-30), which concludes with this report, we developed a project exploitation strategy, described in D8.3 and outlined in section 3 of this report. This strategy outlines key routes for the exploitation of the project's results. Direct activities to exploit results include the development of GEPs, provision of guidelines, datasets and knowledge, as well as indirect results achieved through the implementation in partner organisations (e.g., increased gender balance, increased number of publications authored by women, increased number of publications using gender and sex variables). D8.3 identifies a number of key routes for exploitation.

This report describes our strategy and plan for the **final phase** (M31-54). During this phase, the consortium will work to implement the key routes for exploitation, and ensure that the results are widely communicated to stakeholders and other audiences, thereby increasing the impact of project outputs. This iteration of the DCE plan also includes an evaluation of key performance indicators (benchmarking metrics), along with a publication strategy and plan.

2. Implementing dissemination, communication & exploitation strategy & plan

Communication and scientific dissemination are integral parts of a successful exploitation strategy. The communication strategy complements scientific dissemination by adapting messages and sharing project outputs with a number of audiences, including stakeholders and gatekeepers.

This strategy is iterative and described in D8.1, D8.2, D8.3 & D8.6, with D8.3 describing a set of key routes for exploitation, including:

- Co-creation and implementation of training and mentoring programmes for staff in implementing organisations.
- Sustainable uptake of gender equality plans in implementing partner organisations.
- Scientific publication through books peer review publications.

- Presentation and discussion of objectives and results at conferences, seminars and workshops on the organisational, national and international level.
- Open Access to results and data, either through working papers, or after peer-review publication (for example through the Zenodo platform, strategy outlined in D8.6).
- Policy feedback through a series of policy briefs for national and international audiences and invitation of national and European policy makers to project events (outlined in D8.6).
- Knowledge transfer through MINDtheGEPs Open Forum series for the European gender research community and communication activities, establishing an information repository of recorded presentations on the project website and YouTube (outlined in D8.6).
- Building partner’s capacity to communicate results (outlined in D8.6).
Communication activities to support result dissemination in MINDtheGEPs and sister project channels (e.g., through the project website, social or traditional media).

Initially, as described in D8.3, the scientific publication strategy included a working paper series to share data with the scientific community. However, after discussions in spring 2023, the consortium agreed to instead share data through reports and other scientific publications instead.

3. Communication

The aim of our external communication activities is to disseminate results to a wider set of audiences, generate interest in the project, support and build networks, receive input from stakeholders, refine and develop strategies for dissemination, communication, exploitation and sustainability, as well as inform and influence stakeholder audiences. The approaches, audiences, channels, tools and tactics for the first and second phase are described extensively in D8.6. As described in section 2, we use an iterative approach to developing communication tools and tactics: building on what works. This requires monitoring and evaluation of key performance indicators (KPI’s), that in turn inform our tactics. This report includes an evaluation of metrics for our different channels, and outlines tactics for the third phase of the project.

3.1 Communication tools

The MINDtheGEPs communication tools include a set of channels and formats. Channels include the project website, an e-mail newsletter, Twitter account, YouTube channel, the Open Forum series (described in D8.6), and a recently added dedicated MINDtheGEPs Zenodo community, launched in March 2023, that will play an important role in our result dissemination, as described in 5.4 Open Access to results and data. All channels support project branding through use of the project logo, and implementation of the MINDtheGEPs visual identity (outlined in D8.1 Visual identity and guidelines for use). Additionally, when needed and when opportunities arise, we also leverage our partners’ channels and those of sister projects.

In the third and final phase of the project, the MINDtheGEPs communication strategy will place a greater focus on results (i.e., encompassing everything from ex-ante GEPs to policy briefs, deliverables and scientific publications). The narrative approach adopted in the second phase, which focused on talking *about* our work, will now be complemented by communication about the *actual* results coming out of the project. Notwithstanding, we will maintain emphasis on our taglines ‘Gender equality in research’, ‘No data: No policy!’ and ‘Multiple barriers require multiple actions!’. We are not moving away from the narrative approach but rather adding evidence to strengthen it. The first step in this direction was taken in March 2023, with the publication of the first **MINDtheGEPs policy brief**: [No data: No policies! The MINDtheGEPs approach to evidence-based policies for Gender Equality Plans.](#)

This was followed by the first result dissemination event, during which data supporting the recommendations were presented in the **MINDtheGEPs Open Forum** on 12 May 2023.

These events triggered a **structure update on the website**, with an addition of a ‘Results’ section in the top tab navigation. At the time of writing, the results page showcases partner’s Gender Equality Plans, policy briefs, deliverables and reports, presentations and communication materials. Links from other pages have also been added to support so called ‘roundtrips’, enabling visitors to find what they are looking. For example, there are links to the list of GEPs from the gender equality plans tab in the top navigation (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Examples of roundtrips on the MINDtheGEPs website

3.1 Communication tactics

Communication in the third and final phase of the project will adopt a cross-disciplinary approach to sharing results. The aim is to make the results useful to researchers and research organisations seeking to implement cultural and structural changes to further gender equality at their place of work, even if they are not already part of a GEPs project. This goal also aligns with the narrative approach taken in the second phase of the project, which aimed to provide insights so that people in other fields can learn what it is like to start approaching these issues. As MINDtheGEPs partners begin to produce and publish results, it becomes crucial to find ways to make these results accessible beyond our own field(s).

Tactics to support cross-disciplinary communication involves tailoring the communication of results in different ways for different audiences. This includes producing policy briefs for different stakeholders and decision-makers, providing opportunities for different audiences to engage with experts through the Open Forum, and using social media and website news formats to communicate about activities and results. These tactics ensure that our messages are accessible across different disciplines, professions, and also supports lay people’s understanding. This approach has been successfully employed by the UPP communications team in other research projects, for example the H2020

projects SIENNA (GA NO 741716) and STARBIOS2 (GA NO 709517) as well as the ConcePTION (GA NO 821520) and PREFER (GA NO 115966) projects, funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative, and the RRI workstream of the FP7 FET Flagship Human Brain Project (945539).

In practice, implementing this approach means the addition of a few elements into the project's day-to-day communications:

- Adding results as they become available to the website and Zenodo community
- Writing news items *about* the results to make them make sense to people in other fields
- Making sure results have DOI's through the Zenodo community or through publishers
- Tweeting DOI links of publications to build Altmetric scores to measure online attention
- Sharing results in the Open Forum series
- Building audiences through the Open Forum sign-up forms, by adding a tick-box to sign up to receive news from us in the future

4. Evaluation of communication efforts

The impact of communication & dissemination activities is assessed through key performance indicators for different channels. As part of Task 8.5, WP8 tracks and evaluates key performance indicators for web, social media engagement, views and downloads from Zenodo, publicity, Open Forum attendance and more. In the future, scientific dissemination will also be evaluated using Altmetric data and citations. The aim is to monitor and support an iterative development of dissemination and communications strategy. To ensure we are able to compare our efforts to peers, we also monitor progress by benchmarking against other H2020 projects in terms of audience size and reach.

The **newsletter** uses the Mailchimp platform, which allows us to track how many times a newsletter was opened, and clicks on links. **Twitter** has its own analytics tool that allows us to track how users engage with our content, and the **website** uses SiteImprove analytics data to describe user behaviour. The **YouTube** channel serves as a video repository, that allows us to share and embed video content elsewhere while also tracking views. **Zenodo** provides information on views and downloads, and since all documents are published with a DOI, we are able to track Altmetric data.

As results become available, Altmetrics will become a valuable tool to monitor and evaluate communication efforts. Altmetrics track links to publications and identify in which kinds of channels they appear, e.g. if a DOI link is featured on a blog, in social media, in press, or on Wikipedia pages. Since measuring impact is challenging, Altmetrics scores is a valuable proxy to determine the reach of project outputs and the effectiveness of our communication efforts.

4.1 Website analytics

The MINDtheGEPs website is the primary hub for information and news about the project. At the end of June 2023, the website has over 60 published news items telling the story of the project. Due to issues with the technical platform, and GDPR concerns raised by the Uppsala University IT department who host the website, we were unable to record website user data until June 2022 (further outlined in D8.6). From June 2022-August 2022, Google's Universal Analytics was used. In August 2022, the SiteImprove tool was launched to collect website analytics and the Google data collection was cancelled. This means that data is missing for the initial part of the project.

Website user behaviour from June 2022 shows that the main starting page for users is in fact the main project landing page. User behaviour reflects our change in focus from providing project information to sharing results in spring 2023 (such as gender equality plans and policy briefs) and offering opportunities to engage with experts through our Open Forum launched in October 2022. From the main landing page, 13% of website users go on to read about our work with Gender Equality Plans. The latest web update, which allows users to find partners' ex-ante GEPs from a dedicated landing page explaining how GEPs are developed, has improved the user experience and supports the assumption that our audiences were interested and ready to receive project results.

Figure 2: MINDtheGEPs website page views by month

From June 2022 until May 2023, mindthegeps.eu has collected over 12,000 page views. Peaks in visits to the website align with activity in the project. For example, in September 2022 we shared four news items about success stories in partner organisations, as well as news of the first public Open Forum in October. The Open Forum continued to attract traffic throughout October and November of that year. In March 2023, the number of visits peaked again, this time due to the launch of our first policy brief. In May 2023, we published several translations of that policy brief and also launched the policy brief at the Open Forum.

4.2 Newsletters

Our newsletter serves as the most direct route to reach our audience. The number of subscribers to the newsletter is an indicator for the size of our audience. However, since e-mails can be easily forwarded, we are able to reach a much larger audience, as visible in table 1 below. The "sent to" indicates the subscriber audience, which should be compared to the number of opens by subscribers, with the "total opens" serving as an indicator for forwards.

Building an email subscriber audience is a gradual process. Starting from a list of members of the consortium, by 13 June 2022, we had built an audience of 120 subscribers. By 23 June 2023, this number increased by over 100% to 242. Building an e-mail subscriber audience is challenging. The main tactic we use is an extra tick-box in the Open Forum sign-up forms, asking attendees to sign up to receive news from us in the future. Audience growth correlates to events, while the number of total opens compared to the number of our audience's opens indicates how many interested people our audiences have forwarded the newsletters to.

<i>DATE</i>	<i>TITLE</i>	<i>SENT TO</i>	<i>NO OPENS BY AUDIENCE</i>	<i>NO CLICKS BY AUDIENCE</i>	<i>TOTAL OPENS (INCLUDING FORWARDS)</i>	<i>TOTAL CLICKS (INCLUDING FORWARDS)</i>
11 FEB 2022	Paving the way for gender equality in science	101	51	14	100	20
11 APR 2022	Gender audits & our gender equality vision	108	57	15	356	89
4 OCT 2022	MINDtheGEPs Open Forum on equality and diversity in quantum technologies	126	53	10	222	31
9 NOV 2022	MINDtheGEPs Open Forum on leveraging privilege: advocates, allies, & gender equity	161	79	20	416	47
1 FEB 2023	MINDtheGEPs Open Forum On Large Scale International Research Infrastructures	206	102	19	616	95
19 APR 2023	MINDtheGEPs Open Forum on our approach to evidence-based policies for Gender Equality Plans	239	115	27	421	49

Table 1: Data on newsletter audience, opens and clicks for Q1-Q2 2023

Most clicks are generated by opportunities to join the Open Forum, and the same holds true for forwards. The most successful newsletter thus far, in terms of both opens (proxy for forwards) and clicks, was the 1 February 2023 newsletter advertising the Open Forum on large-scale international research infrastructures on 21 March 2023.

4.3 Twitter

Our most active communication channel is the Twitter channel. It also provides us with an opportunity to benchmark our efforts against those of our peers. Comparisons indicate that the size of a project's audience is only an indicator of how big the reach is, and that quantity (as in the number of tweets) is not necessarily the key to success. Rather, what we share and how we engage our audience are crucial, along with maintain an active presence on the platform to remind our audiences about the project, and reinforce branding. We regularly tweet (Tuesdays and Thursdays at 10 CET), to support brand recognition and establish our presence.

PROJECT	CHANNEL LAUNCHED	NO TWEETS JUNE 2022	FOLLOWERS JUNE 2022	NO TWEETS JUNE 2023	FOLLOWERS JUNE 2023
MINDTHEGEPs (@MINDTHEGEPs_EU)	January 2021	382	437	583	623
RESET (@RESET_EUPROJECT)	March 2021	131	341	314	583
UNISAFE (@UNISAFE_GBV)	February 2021	262	418	688	787
STEPCHANGE (@STEPCHANGEEU)	March 2021	696	403	3,458	769
RESISTIRÉ (RESISTIRE_EU)	June 2021	318	407	739	667
ATHENA EQUALITY (@ATHENA_EQUALITY)	July 2021	116	155	275	384

Table 2: Benchmarking on Twitter (2022-06-13 vs 2023-06-23)

By comparing us against the RESET UNISAFE, STEPCHANGE, RESISTIRÉ and ATHENA EQUALITY projects, we are performing quite well, with 623 followers, we are at par with RESISTIRÉ, a project coming to an end, hosting their final conference on 20-21 June 2023. The UNISAFE and STEPCHANGE projects are surpass us in terms of number of followers. UNISAFE is covering gender-based violence, which makes them stand out a bit thematically among the cluster of H2020 sister projects, likely making it possible for them to tap into other Twitter audience segments. STEPCHANGE is focused on Citizen Science, also setting them apart. However, being in their final six months with an end date in February 2024 and having already published results in scientific journals, they have an advantage, as they are able cater to stakeholder needs for information that they can use in their own work. Speaking for our tactics, centered around sharing results to build our audience and differentiate ourselves from sister project in a saturated Twitter environment (where many H2020 project on gender equality compete for attention), will contribute to our visibility.

Analysing the behaviour of our audience, they seem most responsive when we are offering something valuable to them, such as opportunities to engage with experts, or expert advice. Event promotion is a major driver for engagement on Twitter. An increase in the number of impressions (that is how many times a Tweet has been visible in a Twitter users feed) indicates that we are reaching a broader audience than usual, often attracting new people with content that is relevant to them.

PEAK MONTH(S)	NO. OF IMPRESSIONS	ASSOCIATED PROMOTIONAL CAMPAIGN
FEBRUARY 2021	9,900	Project launch
MARCH 2021	15,000	Project launch event in relation to International Women's Day with Barbara Risman as keynote speaker
JUNE 2021	22,000	Webinar with Elsevier & RELX
OCTOBER 2021	4,100	Promotion of sister project activities.
OCTOBER 2022	3,400	Promotion of Open Forums taking place on 20 October 2022 and 14 December 2022.
MARCH 2023	4,400	Open Forum promotion and International Women's Day.
MAY 2023	4,900	Launch of the first MINDtheGEPs policy brief with accompanying open forum.

Table 3: Peak months on Twitter

The peaks in impressions are related to a lecture by Barbara Risman, Professor and Head of Sociology at the University of Illinois at Chicago, and a webinar organised with Elsevier and RELX. These events offered access to expertise and information that captures attention and prompts our audiences to share with their own followers. Promotion of sister project activities also mobilises the H2020 gender

equality community. Twitter impressions further indicate the success of tactics described in D8.6, demonstrating that the Open Forum series and the Policy Brief launch effectively engaged our audiences and gained visibility on the platform.

4.4 Open Forum

After the pandemic, we have received feedback about “Zoom fatigue”, making it increasingly difficult to recruit participants for online events. However, considering the timing of the launch of our own series of online events, the Open Forum has seen reasonably good attendance and continues to serve as an important tool, not only for dissemination but also for recruiting subscribers to the newsletter. The Open Forum series are recorded and shared on the MINDtheGEPs YouTube channel, on Twitter, and the project website. The recording allows the Open Forum to continue to extend our reach. The data supports the effectiveness of this tactic. So far, 189 people have signed up for the Open Forum, with an added 143 video views of the recorded events, resulting in a 76% increase in our reach.

Title	Date	No of registered	Video views
EQUALITY, DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES	20 October 2022	45	77
LEVERAGING PRIVILEGE: ADVOCATES, ALLIES, & GENDER EQUITY IN UNIVERSITIES	14 December 2022	56	43
LARGE SCALE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES: INHERENTLY DIVERSE?	21 March 2023	47	Event was not recorded.
NO DATA: NO POLICIES! MINDTHEGEPs' APPROACH TO EVIDENCE-BASED POLICIES FOR GENDER EQUALITY PLANS	12 May 2023	41	23

Table 4: Open Forum registrations and video views

The forum has a core audience that is interested in the MINDtheGEPs project, internal stakeholders and interested parties at partner organisations. As we start sharing more of our results, we expect our reach to widen.

4.5 Video on YouTube

As of June 2023, MINDtheGEPs videos have garnered 2,980 impressions (representing the number of times they appeared in people’s YouTube feeds), with 69% (2,066 impressions) stemming from the Open Forum recordings. The total watch time for all videos posted on the channel amounts to 7,6 hours, the majority of which is attributed to Open Forum video, where the three recorded presentations together have a combined watch time of 5,8 hours (clearly correlating to the number of views as shown in table 4). Other videos posted on the channel are short animated presentations of the project in different partner languages, that are all around one minute long.

4.5 Zenodo

On 7 March 2023, the [MINDtheGEPs Zenodo community](#) was launched. Currently, this houses policy briefs, communication materials, posters, and one deliverable report, but it will serve as a repository for more MINDtheGEPs outputs in the future. The community was launched at the end of March. Within three months (28 June), reports on Zenodo had a total of 527 views and 291 downloads. The majority of views and downloads are related to the “No data: No policies! The MINDtheGEPs approach to evidence-based policies for Gender Equality Plans” policy brief(s) in different language versions. These policy briefs were viewed 478 times and downloaded 255 times, suggesting that this tactic (outlined in D8.6) has been successful in sharing results in this format. By requesting partners to translate the briefs into their own language, we enable them to share project results at the national level. Since these documents have DOIs, we will be able to use Altmetric data to evaluate our communication efforts around reports.

Title	Date uploaded	Views	Downloads
Policy brief #1 in English	31 March 2023	324	171
Policy brief #1 in Spanish	25 April 2023	68	34
Policy brief #1 in Serbian	11 May 2023	47	25
Poster: Reducing gender imbalance	7 June 2023	17	10
Poster: Best practices for GEPs	7 June 2023	13	12
Policy brief #1 in Polish	12 June 2023	28	16
Project flyer in Spanish	12 June 2023	11	9
Project flyer in English	12 June 2023	8	6
D3.1 – Guidelines for GEPs' implementation	19 June 2023	11	9

Table 5: MINDtheGEPs Zenodo community – views & downloads of uploaded materials (28 June 2023)

4.6 Implications for DCE activities

It is clear that the audience we have built for our channels through collaborations with sister projects and partners is small, but interested in our area of focus. To expand our reach beyond this group of peers when we have results to deliver, we need to increase the size and extend the reach of our audience. The Open Forum has proven to be effective in this regard, fostering active participation in our online events, building our newsletter subscriber audience, and mobilising newsletter subscribers to forward invitations within their networks. Additionally, the Open Forum has also proved it can engage our Twitter audiences, and data from YouTube demonstrates the value of sharing recorded events.

As outlined in D8.6, reaching beyond our peers requires content that can generate engagement, such as social media shares and e-mail forwards. During the first and second phase, we have saturated the audience growth generated by project branding and information about the scope and structure of MINDtheGEPs. Evaluating the success of the Open Forum, Zenodo community and Policy Brief launch indicates that our audience is indeed ready and eager to receive results from the project. This paves the way for further scientific dissemination, amplified by communication activities, and evaluated using Altmetric data.

5. Scientific dissemination plan

Scientific dissemination is one of the main vehicles for exploiting results from MINDtheGEPs, and a key route for exploitation (as described in D8.3). Section 5 dives into the outreach channels and approaches to enhance the impact of the project's scientific dissemination.

To effectively disseminate and exchange knowledge, consortium members will actively promote and discuss project approaches, methodology, and results at a number of academic and professional conferences within their respective fields. This active engagement is facilitated by the international networks and positions held by the members. This strategy will be supported by Elsevier. For example, by using data and case studies from its own series of reports analysing gender and diversity in research; and providing access to channels that extend the project's reach, for example through the webinar organised jointly with RELX in June 2021 discussed in section 4.3.

As part of the scientific dissemination task (T8.2), WP8 will support the planning and tracking of scientific outputs delivered by project partners between 2021 and 2024 on issues connected to gender equality. The aim is to continuously feed the project's communication channels with the means to deploy the DCE strategy and plan and will be listed on the results web page: <https://www.mindthegeps.eu/results/>. WP8 will also ensure adherence to the open access policy while tracking outreach efforts according to the key performance indicators outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

5.2 MINDtheGEPs Open Forum

The consortium organises a series of webinars to disseminate project results and provide training on various aspects of gender equality plans. These webinars are part of the MINDtheGEPs Open Forum, which serves as a platform for sharing knowledge and are recorded for wider accessibility on the project website and YouTube. These events also play an important role in the communication strategy and contribute to generating publicity and awareness for the project (as described in section 4.4).

The Open Forum format was launched in Q3 2022 to present the first MINDtheGEPs policy brief titled "No data: No policies!". This policy brief outlined the evidence-based approach of MINDtheGEPs towards gender equality plans. Building on this format, the Open Forum will continue to present policy recommendations and engage in discussions, primarily targeting the European gender research community, as well as other relevant projects and initiatives working in the same field.

The preliminary webinar schedule for upcoming Open Forums is as follows:

- September/October: D6.4 – Gendering Scientific Publications Guidelines. Follow up on the Train the Trainers workshop in May 2023, Belgrade.
- November/December: A forum focusing on gender innovations in geology and earth sciences. Dr. Giuliana Rubbia (National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology) will contribute with her presentation titled "[Natural hazards and earthquake science: Gender matters](#)".
- February/March: To be proposed. Work in progress.

5.3 Scientific publication

MINDtheGEPs will disseminate its results through various avenues, including books and open access publications (green or gold) in peer-reviewed topic-related journals. All publications and presentations

of project findings will acknowledge the H2020 programme and the project itself. An Intellectual Property (IP) review processes will be carried out in accordance with the Consortium Agreement, operationalised in guidelines for authorship IP review agreed by the consortium during the project meeting in Belgrade in May 2023.

Additionally, plans are underway for developing of a joint book as part of our project. The preliminary work we have conducted thus far will serve as the foundation for the book's content and structure.

The draft book proposal is currently titled:

- "BREAKING THE GLASS CEILING & OPENING THE FRONT DOOR: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GENDER (IN)EQUALITIES IN RESEARCH AND SCIENCE IN TRADITIONAL COUNTRIES"
[note: possibly in European Periphery. Countries to be outlined]

The book aims to address a unique and appealing specificity. While there are several European projects and publications focusing on gender and research in academia, many of them concentrate on specific disciplinary areas such as STEM or particular aspects of research careers, without taking the following into comprehensive consideration:

- The differences between STEM and SSH.
- The distinctions between academia and other research settings.
- The diverse career paths of women and men in research, encompassing junior, middle, and senior researchers (such as the leaky pipeline, glass door, and glass ceiling).
- The examination of gender imbalances at macro, meso, and micro levels.

Furthermore, a significant proportion of publications on this topic primarily originate from Western Europe and North America, leading to a lack of representation of researchers and academics from peripheral European regions in scholarly discussions. This book aims to contribute to the scholarly debate by focusing on gender regimes in traditional gender countries outside the "core" Europe.

The book will employ a theoretical lens to examine gender imbalances in research performing organizations (RPO) at different levels:

- MICRO – Individual level: Examining individual beliefs, practices, preferences, and strategies.
- MESO – Interactional and working organization level: Analyzing interactions and prevailing cultures within work organizations.
- MACRO – Cultural and institutional level: Investigating the institutional and cultural settings at the national level.

The draft structure includes the following sections:

INTRODUCTION:

Studying gender (in)equalities in research and science in different contexts.

PART 1 – PAINTING A QUANTITATIVE PORTRAIT: ITALY, POLAND, IRELAND, SPAIN, AND SERBIA AT THE GENDER LENS

Chapter 1: Mapping the macro context: Varieties of gender regimes.

Chapter 2: Collecting multi-area indicators at the meso-level: Towards the design and monitoring of gender equality policies.

Chapter 3: How research careers work and should work? A web survey on researchers' views.

Chapter 4: Which policies matter? The perspectives of governance and researchers.

PART 2 – PAINTING A QUALITATIVE PORTRAIT: ITALY, POLAND, IRELAND, SPAIN, SERBIA, AND THE 'GENDER TROUBLE'

Chapter 1: The glass door: Exploring gendered paths of precariousness in different academic contexts.

Chapter 2: The glass ceiling: A comparative analysis across different types of organisations.

Chapter 3: Work-life balance: Examining the motherhood penalty and parenthood resistance.

Chapter 4: Defining and experiencing productivity and excellence: Comparing the views of early and advanced career researchers.

PART 3 – MAKING SCIENCE IN THE NEOLIBERAL AGE: CRITICALITIES AND LINES OF FLIGHT

Chapter 1: Criticalities: Being a researcher in the neoliberal age - The "publish or perish" model and the weight of unpaid work.

Chapter 2: Criticalities: Fixing women or fixing the system? The case of mentoring.

Chapter 3: Lines of flight: Feminist epistemologies for gendering science and changing the system.

Chapter 4: Lines of flight: Good practices in MINDtheGEPs' gender equality plans.

CONCLUSIONS:

Multi-level policies for opening the front door and breaking the glass.

We are expecting the book to be ready by the end of the project, working according to the following timeline:

- Q3 2023: Conclude abstract and submit proposal.
- Q1 2024: First draft of chapters.
- Q2 2024: Workshop for discussion of chapters.
- Q3 2024: Final version of chapters.

5.4 Open Access to results and data

MINDtheGEPs Open Access repository: In spring 2023, MINDtheGEPs launched a Zenodo community, to ensure open access to results and data. Zenodo will be used for sharing public deliverable reports, policy briefs and other publications from the project in a sustainable way. Through Zenodo, all publications receive a DOI and become indexed in OpenAire. DOI-links will also allow WP8 to track and monitor Altmetric data, collecting data on attention, in addition to metrics on views and downloads provided by the repository. Documents uploaded to Zenodo will be linked from the MINDtheGEPs website, ensuring they are easily found.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the MINDtheGEPs community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The main heading is 'MINDtheGEPs: Gender equality in research'. Below this, a 'Recent uploads' section lists three items:

- MINDtheGEPs D3.1 – Guidelines for GEPs' implementation** (June 16, 2023, v1, Project deliverable, Open Access). Authors: Di Tullio, Ilaria; Pisacane, Lucio; Marchesini, Nicolò; Cellini, Marco; Tagliacozzo, Serena. Description: This deliverable is a product of MINDtheGEPs. It is meant to provide MINDtheGEPs partner organisations with a useful tool for the development of a Gender Equality Plan. Considering the European Commission legislation concerning Gender Equality and the Horizon Europe eligibility criteria, t. Uploaded on June 19, 2023.
- Reducing gender imbalance in the research community** (June 12, 2023, v1, Other, Open Access). Description: MINDtheGEPs consortium; MINDtheGEPs will reduce gender imbalances in European research institutions and generate data to support the development of national and European policy for gender equality in research performing organisations. Uploaded on June 12, 2023.
- Reducir el desequilibrio de género en la comunidad investigadora** (June 12, 2023, v1, Other, Open Access). Description: MINDtheGEPs consortium;

On the right side, there is a 'New upload' button and a community profile for 'MINDtheGEPs gender equality in research'. The profile includes a description: 'MINDtheGEPs (Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 101006543. We are working to reduce gender imbalances in European research institutions and generate data to support the development of national and European policies for gender equality in research-performing organisations.' The curator is listed as 'crd_uu'.

Figure 3: MINDtheGEPs Zenodo community

6. References

- Fernow J, Holm A & Zarzosa G, D8.1 – Visual identity and guidelines for use, MINDtheGEPs 2021
- Fernow J & Holm A, D8.2 – Dissemination and communication plan, MINDtheGEPs 2021
- Fernow J, Colaciomo C & Holm A, D8.6 – Dissemination and exploitation plan update, MINDtheGEPs 2022
- Fernow J, Santinhos M, Solera C & Y Colonnello C, D8.3 – Exploitation plan, MINDtheGEPs 2023

Annex 1

MINDtheGEPs Publications Agreement

This document intends to establish consortium policies on publications and authorship, as a result as an agreement among partners. The spirit is to encourage a large publication of scientific articles in peer reviewed journals as well as other kind of publications (i.e., chapters in edited books, conference papers, etc.) based on the MINDtheGEPs research data without causing any prejudice to the Consortium members but wishing to spread the name of the project and of the consortium member as much as possible.

The main priority of the consortium must be the obligation to protect results, to maintain the confidentiality and the security of personal data as stated in art. 26, 27, 36 and 39 on Grant Agreement and on related project deliverables (D 9.1, D 9.2). In order to ensure this, appropriate measures for processing, handling and storing data have to be central at all stages of the research and beyond, as declared in D 1.2.

Furthermore, accordingly to the *Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access* in H2020 programs, MINDtheGEPs has to ensure open access to data (the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement) and to scientific publication (each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results).

PROCEDURE FOR SUBMITTING SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES AND OTHER KIND OF PUBLICATIONS

a) Information on publication to other partners

The Consortium Agreement provisions at art 8.4.2.1 states that prior notice of any planned publication shall be given, including title, author(s), abstract (in English) and journal, of the proposed publication, to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the intended date of publication. In order to facilitate the coordination of publishing efforts, Consortium members are invited to communicate to the Coordinator their intention to publish/prepare a publication as soon as they start to work on the paper(s). Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted. This includes publication of confidential deliverable reports, whole or in parts, where partners can request an embargo on publishing reports, or parts of thereof, in case disclosing information could impede other publication plans.

According to CA 8.4.2.2, an objection is justified if:

- (a) the protection of the objecting Party's Results or Background would be adversely affected
- (b) the objecting Party's Legitimate interests in relation to the Results or Background would be significantly harmed.

The objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

If an objection has been raised the involved Parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by

protecting information before publication) and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion. The objecting Party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that Confidential Information of the objecting Party has been removed from the Publication as indicated by the objecting Party.

b) Request of permission for the use of other partners' datasets

Partners intending to publish articles based on (or partially based on) other partners' datasets (for example in comparison essays) shall inform the partner about this intention. Qualitative and quantitative data sets may be made available for publication: however, there is no obligation to translate in English qualitative data sets (e.g. raw data like interviews' or focus groups' transcripts). The expectation is that research teams will not normally deny other consortium members the opportunity to use their data for the purposes of these kinds of analyses. It is recommended, however, to communicate both to the Coordinator and to the team(s) whose data are being used, the intention to publish on their data set(s).

c) Open Access to scientific publications

As soon as the editors accept your peer-reviewed scientific research articles, notify immediately the Coordinator and the WP8 leaders who will keep a record of the publications, for the purposes of updating the "Scientific publications table" in the periodic report and the DMP. At this stage, or at the latest upon publication, consortium members must deposit a machine readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications– institutional, disciplinary or public - which shall be compliant with OpenAIRE requirements Gold and green rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications apply. Open Access policies are not mandatory (even though recommended) for **other types of scientific publications** including: monographs, books, conference proceedings, grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports).

d) Open Access to Research Data

Simultaneously consortium members must deposit the portion of, or the whole dataset used for the publication, in the online repository mentioned in the DMP and respecting licensing and metadata described in the DMP. **Granting open access to Research Data is mandatory for any kind of scientific publication.** Datasets should be prepared following the rules and the principles outlined in the DMP (D1.2): i.e. ethical requirements, privacy issues, language etc. Particular attention should be given to qualitative data that should be anonymised, or made only partially available due to privacy protection when necessary.

AUTHORSHIP

Below are reported four possible scenarios of publication and the related provisions on the authorship agreed by the Consortium.

1. Scientific publication reporting the data and the analysis of the data collected by one team in the consortium.

Authorship:

Normally, it would include the team leader of the institution that collected the data; other members of the local research team who have contributed sufficiently to the work to merit inclusion.

Acknowledgement to be included as footnote:

The research reported in this paper is based on the findings of the MINDtheGEPs project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101006543 (www.mindthegeps.eu). The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. Authors would like to thank (*WPLeader(s)'name*) for the intellectual contribution made in the development of the research rationale and measures.

Ownership of data: The local research team and the Work Package Leader(s)

2. Scientific publication reporting data and the analysis of the data collected by two or more teams in the consortium.

Authorship:

Partners intending to publish on the data collected by two or more teams shall inform the leader of all the teams in the consortium whose data are being used in the paper which are not yet in the open domain.

Only researchers who decided to jointly work on the drafting of the article will be credited as authors. Partners who collected the data, not interested in working on the article, will not be cited as author. However, their name will appear in the acknowledgements (see below).

Acknowledgement to be included as footnote:

The research reported in this paper is based on the findings of the MINDtheGEPs project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101006543 (www.mindthegeps.eu). The author(s) would like to thank (*WP leader(s)*) for the intellectual contribution made in the development of the research rationale and measures and (*team leaders of the institutions that provided the datasets*) for the data which were collected by their team to be used in this paper.

Ownership of data: The research teams that collected the data.

3. Interpretative or theoretical papers based on the findings of the project, which may or may not report further analyses of the data collected by teams in the consortium.

Authorship: The individuals who have generated the interpretations and theoretical positions which are described in the paper. However, these individuals should inform the leader of any team whose data is being analyzed in the paper if these are not yet made open.

WP leader(s) and Team leaders in the consortium who provided the datasets will be acknowledged as specified below.

Acknowledgement to be included as footnote:

(if the papers include new analyses on the datasets) The research reported in this paper is based on the findings of the MINDtheGEPs project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101006543 (www.mindthegeps.eu). The author(s) would like to thank (*WP leader(s)*) for the intellectual contribution made in the development of the research rationale and measures and (*team leaders in the consortium who provided the datasets*) for the data which were collected by their team to be used in this paper. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

(if the paper does not include new analyses on the datasets) The contents of this paper are based on the findings of the MINDtheGEPs project which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101006543 (www.mindthegeps.eu). The author(s) would like to thank (*WP leader(s)*) for the intellectual contribution made in the development of the research rationale and measures. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

5. Scientific publications related to the MINDtheGEPs case-studies

Authorship:

Normally, it would include the team leader of the institution that carried out the case-study; other members of the local research team who have contributed sufficiently to the work to merit inclusion.

Acknowledgement to be included as footnote:

The research reported in this paper was funded by

The integration of the sex/gender variables in the research was promoted by the MINDtheGEPs project which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101006543 (www.mindthegeps.eu). The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Authors would like to thank (*WP Leader(s)’name*) for the intellectual contribution made in the development of the research rationale and measures.

Ownership of data: The local research team.

Notes

Order of authorship

A publication can be proposed and carried-on by a principal investigator and/or by a corresponding author and can include other contributors. Normally, the first-named author will be the person who takes the primary responsibility for producing the paper and, in particular, is responsible for producing the first submittable draft of the manuscript.

Recommendation on citations

All consortium members should make every effort to cite the work of MINDtheGEPs colleagues in their own writings, in order to maximize references to, and the exposure of, the MINDtheGEPs project within the research literature.

DESCRIPTION OF PROCESS FOR SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION

45 days before publication or submission to journal	
Checklist for authors	Roles and responsibilities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Include acknowledgement and disclaimer ● Share title, author(s), abstract (in English) and name of journal or report with partners using this list: partners-mindthegeps.cirsde@unito.it ● If no objections within 30 days, go ahead with publication or submit to journal ● Ensure open access to research data ● Save a copy of the submitted publication for parallel publication in open access repository ● Share your manuscript with the WP8 comms team to plan publicity ● When the paper is published, send link to josepine.fernnow@crb.uu.se for publicity activities & federica.turco@unito.it for reporting 	<p>Author: Give notice to partners, including title, author(s), abstract (in English) and name of journal</p> <p>Partners: Right to object within 30 days. Right to ask for a 90 day embargo/delay of publication.</p> <p>Project management: Check of acknowledgement and disclaimers</p> <p>Communication team: Plan publicity</p>